

Dynamic Properties of the Voter Model with Stochastic Activation of Links Driven by Avalanche-like Perturbations

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In this paper, we study the dynamical modes of the modified noisy voter model. In our model, the changes in the binary state (opinion) of the voters (agents) are caused by the avalanche-like dynamics of the threshold variables (tensors) assigned to them. The system under study is considered as a scale-free network in which the nodes represent elements (agents, voters) and the edges represent possible contacts between the elements. The structure of the links between voters is not static. Its temporal evolution is due to the “activity” of the agents. This property determines the probability that an agent is connected to its nearest neighbors at a given time. Within the model, an agent that is not linked to neighbors can change its opinion to an opposite one, regardless of the opinions of other agents. A linked agent can copy the opinion of its neighbor during an avalanche process. Analytically and numerically, we show that the value of agents’ “activity” completely determines the mode of opinion dynamics. We derive a critical value of the “activity” at which there is a transition between two dynamic regimes of the system. In the first case, the system switches between two consensus states. In the opposite case, the system tends to a state where opposing opinions coexist and the system-averaged opinion is zero. We show that the analytical approach describes the behavior of the system qualitatively well.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, methods and models of statistical physics, developed to study nonlinear non-equilibrium systems consisting of a large number of interacting elements, are actively used in other sciences including biology, chemistry, ecology, and even social sciences [1]. The models usually chosen for interdisciplinary studies are rather simple. However, they reflect quite well the mechanisms that determine the occurrence of collective effects in each specific case. A classic example of this type of model is the voter model [2], [3]. Originally formulated for a biological system, this model and its modifications have

been widely used to study opinion dynamics [4]. In the original version of the model, identical voters (agents) form a network. At each step in the evolution of the system, a randomly chosen agent switches between two states of opinion by copying the state of its neighbor, also chosen at random. This basic voter model has become a paradigm for studying the transition to consensus in a population [5].

A number of modifications have been proposed to bring the model closer to reality. One such modification is a noisy voter model [6]. In this version, an agent can not only copy the state of neighboring agents but in addition has the possibility to switch opinion spontaneously and independently from the opinions of its neighbors. The main feature of the noisy voter

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model dynamics is that, evolving according to proposed rules, the system under consideration never reaches a stable state, but migrates through the ensemble of metastable states. Two switching mechanisms compete with each other. Copying brings the system into consensus state, independent updating leads to a disordered state. Different dynamic modes occur depending on the relationship between two switching processes. The necessity to take into account the different strategies for agents action arises not only for description of opinion dynamics [7], but also for modelling economic processes, such as price formation and fluctuations or the stability of financial markets[8] and in the game theory [9].

However, within the noisy voter model, an agent that changes its mind at a given evolutionary step is usually chosen randomly. It is also random whether the agent changes its opinion under the influence of the environment or independently of it. In the real system, however, the situation is quite different. This fact led us to modify the noisy voter model to take into account the reasons that cause the agent to change its state in a certain way at a certain time. We were guided by the following assumptions. The most natural reason for a person to act, and in particular to change opinion, is the pressure of information received. The information pressure on a person changes by exchanging information with other people (e.g. neighbors) or by receiving information from external sources. As the spread of information is often seen as an avalanche-like process [10], we assume that the information pressure on people in a population also changes like an avalanche. We also assume that a person who communicates with his neighbors tends to copy their opinions; the isolated person forms his opinion independently.

To model such a case, we consider the set of interacting voters (agents), each of which is assigned a binary variable as an “opinion”. In contrast to the voter model, however, agents can only change their opinion as a result of an avalanche-like change in other characteristics, represented by threshold variables (“pressure”).

The switching rules are as follows. If an agent is unlinked with its neighbors, but its pressure exceeds the defined threshold, it changes its opinion to the opposite. An agent that is linked with its neighbors can change its opinion to that of the neighbor that increases the pressure on it during the avalanche.

To incorporate new mechanisms into the noisy voter model, we modify it as follows. We assume that the agents form a scale-free network with a time-varying structure of links. At any time, each agent can be connected or disconnected to its nearest neighbors. The probability for an agent to activate links with its nearest neighbors per unit of time is defined by a new property - the agent’s “activity”. The evolution of the network is described by an algorithm first proposed in [11] for modeling activity-driven temporal networks. The avalanche-like pressure changes occur according to the algorithms of the Olami-Feder-Christensen earthquake model [12] modified for the activity-driven network. Earlier we studied such a type of system on the activity-driven square lattice [13]. In this paper the avalanche-like dynamics was modeled by algorithms of the Abelian sandpile model [14].

The present work aims at investigating the dynamic properties of the proposed model. As a result, we will show analytically and by computer simulation that, for fixed topological characteristics of the network, the opinion dynamics modes are completely determined by the “activity” of the agents. This fact demonstrates the possibility of controlling the system dynamics by manipulating the agents’ “activities”.

The paper is organized as follows. The next section presents a description of the dynamic process under consideration and the algorithms of the proposed model. The third section contains the analytical results of studying the dynamic regimes that arise in the model. In the fourth section we present the results of numerical simulation of system behavior for various values of “activities” and compare ones with obtained analytical estimations. In conclusion the main

results of the work are formulated and the perspectives and possibilities of its applications are discussed.

2. Model

We consider a multi-agent system of L interacting agents located at the nodes of a scale-free network. The agents are numbered by index i . The network is constructed by means of linear preferential attachment [15] and resulting distribution of nodes degrees (l_i) demonstrates the power-law dependence $P(l) \sim l^{-\gamma}$, $\gamma \approx 3$. Each agent (node) is assigned two dynamic variables: a binary variable $s_i(k) = \pm 1$, denoting the opinion of this agent, and a threshold variable $z_i(k)$, representing the value of information pressure experienced by the agent. The threshold values for all agents are the same and are equal to z_c . The discrete variable k denotes the time in our system, the time step we set as $\Delta k = 1$. Before the beginning of the evolution process we assign for each agent an “activity” $a_i = a$ defined as the probability for the i -th agent to activate links with its network neighbors per time step.

At the initial time $k = 0$ we arbitrarily set the values $z_i(0)$ ($z_i(0) \in [0, z_c)$) and $s_i(0)$ at each agent ($\sum_i s_i = 0$).

The following algorithms describe the dynamics of information pressure and agents’ opinions [16].

1. Increasing pressure.

All $z_i(k)$ increase by a random value Δz_i , uniformly distributed over the interval $[0, 2/L]$. This process, as well as the avalanche following it, is numbered by the index n , and $k = k_{beg}^n$ is the moment of the beginning of the n -th avalanche and $k = k_{end}^n$ is end moment of the n -th avalanche.

$$\begin{aligned} \forall(i) : z_i(k = k_{end}^{n-1}) &\rightarrow z_i(k_{end}^{n-1} + 1 = k_{beg}^n) \\ &= z_i(k_{end}^{n-1}) + \Delta z_i, \Delta z_i \in [0, 2/L]. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

2. “Active” agents form a subnetwork. “Inactive” agents change their opinion.

2.1 At time k_{beg}^n , each agent becomes “active” with probability a and activates links with nearest neighbors, regardless of whether they are “active” or not. A subnetwork G_n appears, which is a set of connected clusters with “active” and “inactive” agents.

The function $\delta_i(k)$ describes the “activity” state of (i)-th agent at the time moment k .

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_i(k_{beg}^n) &= 1 \text{ with probability } a; \\ \delta_i(k_{beg}^n) &= 0 \text{ with probability } (1 - a). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Note, that during an avalanche $\delta_i(k) = \delta_{i,j}(k_{beg}^n)$.

2.2 All “inactive” agents for which $z_i(k_{beg}^n) \geq z_c$ (supercritical agents) change their opinion to the opposite one

if $\delta_i(k_{beg}^n) = 0$ and $z_i(k_{beg}^n) \geq z_c$, then

$$s_i(k_{beg}^n) \rightarrow s_i(k_{beg}^n + 1) = -s_i(k_{beg}^n). \quad (3)$$

3. An avalanche.

3.1 If the value of the pressure at any “active” agent of the G_n exceeds the critical value, then the pressure on it decreases to 0 (the agent topples). Subsequently, the pressure is redistributed uniformly among the l_i neighbors of the toppling node, and the fraction α of $z_i(k)$ dissipates.

“Active” agents that are the neighbors of the toppling agent change their opinions to the opinion of this agent.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{if } z_i(k) \geq z_c \text{ then } z_i(k) &\rightarrow z_i(k + 1) = 0; \\ z_{nn(i)}(k) &\rightarrow z_{nn(i)}(k + 1) = z_{nn(i)}(k) + \alpha z_i(k)/l_i; \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

if $\delta_{nn(i)}(k) = 1$, then

$$s_{nn(i)}(k) \rightarrow s_{nn(i)}(k + 1) = -s_{nn(i)}(k) \quad (5)$$

where index $nn(i)$ depicts neighbors of i -th agent.

If there are several “active” supercritical agents in the G_n at time k , they topple

simultaneously. This process takes a unit time and is called an avalanche wave. The pressure for currently “inactive” agents can increase due to topplings of their supercritical neighbors, but they cannot topple themselves.

3.2 We repeat step 3.1 until all “active” agents of the subnetwork G_n become stable, i.e. $z_i(k) < z_c$ for them. Then the avalanche ends and we go to step 4.

4. End of an avalanche.

When the avalanche ends, all links in the existing subnetwork are canceled and we repeat steps 1-4.

We assume that cancelation and activation of links occurs instantaneously. Then, each subnetwork G_n exists for a certain time equal to the number of waves in the given avalanche. The “inactive” agents receiving the information from “active” neighbors can remain supercritical at the end of the avalanche. Later these agents can become “active” and give rise to new toppling cascades during the next avalanche.

To describe the collective dynamics in our model, we will use two main characteristics: the average opinion over the system at the end of the n -th avalanche $m(n)$ and the normalized size of the n -th avalanche $s(n)$:

$$m(n) = \frac{1}{L} \sum_i s_i(k_{end}^n) \quad (6)$$

where $s_i(k_{end}^n)$ is the agent’s opinion at node (i) at the end of the n -th avalanche.

$$s(n) = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{k=k_{beg}^n}^{k=k_{end}^n} \sum_{(i) \in G_n} \delta_i(k) \theta[z_i(k) - z_c]; \quad (7)$$

$$\theta[z_i(k) - z_c] = 1 \text{ if } z_i \geq z_c;$$

$$\theta[z_i(k) - z_c] = 0 \text{ if } z_i < z_c.$$

Here the first summation is performed over all waves of the avalanche from its beginning $k = k_{beg}^n$ to the end $k = k_{end}^n$, and the second — by the nodes of the sublattice G_n . Thus, the quantity s_n is the normalized to the lattice size total number of nodes that topples during the avalanche. The toppling node will be taken into account as many times as it toppled during the avalanche.

3. Analytical results

In order to understand what kinds of regimes of collective dynamics can arise in our model, we carry out some analytical estimates. For this analytical study we consider the time evolution of the averaged opinion calculated as $m(t) = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i,j} s_{i,j}(t)$. Note, that the time notation t emphasizes that now the time step Δt can take any value. Since the dynamics of our system is stochastic, we will characterize it by the function $\rho(m, t)$ — the probability density for the average opinion over the system to have the value m at moment t . Following the receipt usually used for the voter models we obtain an analytical expression for $\rho(m, t)$ by solving the Fokker-Planck equation.

During the interval Δt the value m can increase or decrease by Δm , or remain the same. Then we get the following relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(m, t + \Delta t) = & (1 - w^-(m) - w^+(m))\rho(m, t) \\ & + w^+(m - \Delta m)\rho(m - \Delta m, t) \\ & + w^-(m + \Delta m)\rho(m + \Delta m, t) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where the functions $w^\pm(m)$ determine the probability that m will increase (decrease) by Δm during the time interval Δt . Then, for the small value $\Delta m \sim L^{-1}$ we can write:

$$\frac{\rho(m, t + \Delta t) - \rho(m, t)}{\Delta t} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial m} \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta t} (w^+(m) - w^-(m)) \rho(m, t) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial m^2} \frac{\Delta m^2}{\Delta t} (w^+(m) + w^-(m)) \rho(m, t). \quad (9)$$

Taking $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, we obtain the Fokker-Planck equation for $\rho(m, t)$, and expression for the stationary probability density $\rho^{st}(m)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho(m, t) &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial m} \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta t} (w^+(m) - w^-(m)) \rho(m, t) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial m^2} \frac{\Delta m^2}{\Delta t} (w^+(m) + w^-(m)) \rho(m, t); \\ \rho^{st}(m) &= C \exp\left(-L \int \frac{-F(m') + D'(m')/L}{D(m')} dm'\right), \\ F(m) &= w^+ - w^-; D(m) = w^+ + w^- \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where C is a normalization constant, which is obtained from the condition $\int_{-1}^1 \rho^{st}(m) dm = 1$.

To analyze the behavior of $\rho^{st}(m)$ depending on the characteristics of the system, it is necessary to determine the functions $w^\pm(m)$. These quantities can be expressed from the probabilities for the agent to change its opinion from $s_i = \pm 1$ to $s_i = \mp 1$:

$$w_i^+ = \frac{a_i}{2} \sum_j A_{ij} \rho_j^a a_j (1 + s_j) + \frac{1}{2} (1 - a_i) \rho_i^a (1 - s_i), w^+ = \sum_{i:s_i=-1} w_i^+, \quad (11)$$

$$w_i^- = \frac{a_i}{2} \sum_j A_{ij} \rho_j^a a_j (1 - s_j) + \frac{1}{2} (1 - a_i) \rho_i^a (1 + s_i), w^- = \sum_{i:s_i=1} w_i^- \quad (12)$$

where A_{ij} is the adjacent matrix of the initial network, ρ_i^a is the probability for the agent to be supercritical.

Now, having these expressions, we make a number of rough simplifying assumptions and consider the mean-field-like approach. We introduce the following quantities: $\rho^\pm(t)$ — the part of agents with positive and negative opinions, respectively, where $m(t) = \rho^+(t) - \rho^-(t)$, and $\rho^+(t) + \rho^-(t) = 1$. We assume that for all agents the probability of the toppling can be estimated as the average avalanche size $\rho_i^a(t) a_i = \langle s \rangle$. We also fix the number of “inactive” supercritical agents at the end of the n -th avalanche as its average value over the evolutionary time $(1 - a) \rho^a(k_{end}^n) = (1 - a)^2 \langle s \rangle / a$ [17]. Then, we

can write the following expressions for $w^\pm(m)$:

$$w^+ = a \langle s \rangle \langle l \rangle \rho^+ \rho^- + \rho^- \frac{(1 - a)^2}{a} \quad (13)$$

$$w^- = a \langle s \rangle \langle 1 \rangle \rho^+ \rho^- + \rho^+ \frac{(1 - a)^2}{a} \quad (14)$$

$$F(m) = w^+ - w^- = -m \frac{(1 - a)^2 \langle s \rangle}{a}, \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} D(m) = w^+ + w^- &= \frac{1}{2} \langle s \rangle a \langle l \rangle (1 - m^2) \\ &+ \frac{(1 - a)^2 \langle s \rangle}{a}. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The averaged value $\langle l \rangle$ for scale-free network we take as $\langle l \rangle = 2l_{min}$.

Substituting (15) and (16) into (10), after taking the integral, one can obtain an expression

for the stationary probability density $\rho^{st}(m)$:

$$\rho^{st}(m) \sim \frac{1}{\langle s \rangle a l_{min} (1 - m^2) + \frac{(1-a)^2 \langle s \rangle}{a} (P-1)}, \quad (17)$$

$$P = L \frac{(1-a)^2}{a^2 l_{min}}. \quad (18)$$

From (17) we get the critical value for the activity $a_c = \frac{1}{1 + \sqrt{(l_{min})/L}}$, so that for $a > a_c$ the stationary probability density $\rho^{st}(m)$ has two maxima at $m_{1,2}^* = 1$, for $a < a_c$ the only maximum at $m_0^* = 0$, and for $a = a_c$ $\rho^{st} = const$. This means that the model has three dynamical regimes. In the “ordered” regime, corresponding to the bimodal form of $\rho^{st}(m)$, the probabilities for the system to be in the states with $m(n) = m_{1,2}^* = \pm 1$ are equal. Transitions between these states take negligible time. In the “disordered” regime, corresponding to the unimodal $\rho^{st}(m)$, the system is in a state of dynamical balance. This means that most of the time the number of agents with the opinion $s_i(t) = 1$ in the system is equal to the number of agents with the opinion $s_i(t) = -1$, but the values of $s_i(t)$ at the nodes can change. In critical mode, all values for $m \in [-1, 1]$ have the same probability.

4. Computer simulation results

Simulations were carried out for network of size $L = 2500$ with different values of l_{min} ($l_{min} = 10; 5; 2$). We fix $z_c = 4.5$ and $\alpha = 0.98$. In all considered cases, evolving according to the algorithms described above, the system reaches a stationary unstable state. In this state the average pressure at the end of the n -th avalanche $z(k_{end}^n) = \frac{1}{L} \sum z_i(k_{end}^n)$ only slightly fluctuates around its value averaged over avalanches z_{av} . The probability density for $z(k_{end}^n)$ has a Gaussian form. Such a criteria of the stationarity is usually used for the OFC-model model. In this state, we followed the system during N_{av} avalanches, and the value N_{av} changed within $10^7 - 10^9$ avalanches. We have studied the dynamics of our system for various values of a .

At the end of each avalanche we calculate the averaged agents’ opinion (6). After the end of system evolution the probability density $\rho^{st}(m)$ is calculated. The figure 1 shows the probability density functions $\rho^{st}(m)$ for different values of a and network of size $L = 2500$ and $l_{min} = 5$. The bottom panel of each graph shows the behavior of $m(n)$ in the relevant cases.

We see that for $a = 0.9$ (figure 1a)) the function $\rho^{st}(m)$ has two maxima of the same height at the values $m_{1,2}^*$. The behavior of $m(n)$ (figure 1d)) shows that the system spends most of its evolution time in states with $m_{1,2}^*$, transitions between these states are relatively fast. In the case of $a = 0.75$ (figure 1c)) the function $\rho^{st}(m)$ has a single maximum, which corresponds to $m_0^* = 0$ and $m(n)$ fluctuates around this value (figure 1f)). The figures 1b and 1e illustrate the critical mode. It corresponds to $a_c \approx 0.87$. As a criterion for the system to be in critical state we take the condition that for the averaged absolute value of m we have $\langle |m| \rangle \approx 0.5$ and the standard deviation for this quantity takes the value $\sigma(|m|) \approx 0.2886$.

In the cases $l_{min} = 10$ and $l_{min} = 2$, we obtained qualitatively similar results, but with $a_c(l_{min} = 10) \approx 0.83$ and $a_c(l_{min} = 2) \approx 0.93$.

Thus, the obtained numerical results demonstrate that the analytical approach used above is suitable for a qualitative description of the system, but gives an overstated quantitative results. This is due to the fact that we used the average values for the key statistical characteristics of the system and neglected their fluctuations.

5. Conclusion

We have studied the dynamic regimes in the modified noisy voter model driven by avalanche-like perturbations. The model is a symbiosis of the noisy voter model [21] and OFC-model [12] on the time-varying network. The temporal evolution of the network is driven by a new characteristic of the agent – “activity”. It determines the probability for the agent to be linked with its

FIG. 1: The probability density function of the system-averaged opinion in the stationary state $\rho^{st}(m)$ for a system of size $L = 2500$ and $l_{min} = 5$ a) $a = 0.9 > a_c$, b) $a = 0.86 = a_c$, c) $a = 0.85 < a_c$. The bottom panel of each graph shows fragments of the $m(n)$ series for the corresponding values of a .

nearest neighbors at a given time moment. We have considered the simplest case where the values of “activity” are the same for all agents.

The main result of the paper is the demonstration that for the network of finite size the dynamics of the system is controlled by the value of the “activity” of the agents. We have shown that three dynamical modes arise in the model. The system dynamics are ordered when the value of agents’ ”activity” is larger than a critical one. In this case, the system switches between the consensus states, spending the most of time in the consensus with shared opinion corresponding to the prevailing external opinion. For the case where the ”activity” of the agents is smaller than the critical value system tends to the disordered state where the opposite opinions coexist. In the critical regimes all values of averaged opinion occur with the same probability. The critical value for ”activity” depends on the averaged degree of the nodes. It decreases as this quantity increases.

The “activity” of agents can be interpreted as the fraction of agents who have chosen one of the two strategies to change their opinion. The ability to control this value is important, for example, in studies of the stability of financial markets [18], the dynamics of market prices [8], the “echo chamber” effect in social networks [20]. Thus, the main advantage of the presented model is that

the parameter that governs the dynamics of the system can be easily manipulated, even in a real system. A two-way voting process in a community of people influenced by their environment and a decision-making process in a group of traders under market pressure are examples of behavior that can be described by the proposed model.

In addition our model give the opportunity to consider the process of opinion formation under conditions never considered early. For example, in our previous work [13], we have studied the influence of the lifetime of activated links on the system behavior. In addition, the proposed model makes it possible to consider the systems with of time-varying “activities” of agents or diverse critical values for the pressure for different agents or to study the system on complex temporal networks with diverse correlations properties. We think that the possible generalizations are the new steps to make the model more realistic.

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